

For a given kinetic run, the concentration of sulphuric and acid oxalic acid will be constant. The equation (v) may be written as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{Ce(IV)}]}{dt} = k[\text{Ce(IV)}] \quad \dots(\text{vi})$$

Which is experimental rate equation for disappearance of Ce(IV) ion.

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Solid State Studies on Polymerization and Depolymerization of 12-Heteropoly Molybdochromate (III)

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THE present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of a new condensation inorganic polymer, $\text{K}_5[\text{CrMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 36\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The oxidation state of chromium has been established by E.S.R. method and the studies on thermal depolymerization of the compound has also been carried. Of condensation inorganic polymer¹, very few references on heteropoly molybdochromate² are found in the literature. The present note is an attempt towards that line.

To 80 ml. of M/15 potassium dichromate solution, 50 ml. of M/10 aqueous solution of molybdic acid and 10 ml. of '20 volume' hydrogen peroxide solution was gradually added with constant stirring at a controlled temperature of 80° in a thermostat. The stirring was continued for two hours and then the solution was left for three days in vacuum, when orange coloured needle shaped crystalline compound came out which was recrystallised thrice from hot water. The analysis of the compound was carried out by usual chemical and colorimetric methods. Estimation of potassium has also been corroborated by flame photometric method. (Found : K, 7.10 ; Mo, 42.65 ; Cr, 1.80 ; H, 2.50% Cald. for $\text{K}_5[\text{CrMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 36\text{H}_2\text{O}$: K, 7.25 ; Mo, 42.87 ; Cr, 1.93 ; H, 2.67%). Hydrogen has been estimated by element

estimation method and molybdenum has been determined by colorimetric method³. From the analytical data, the molecular formula of the compound, as per Keggin's view³, comes out to be $\text{K}_5[\text{CrMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}] \cdot 36\text{H}_2\text{O}$, which may be named as 12-heteropoly molybdochromate.

Molecular Weight Determinations : The molecular weight of the polymeric compound has been determined accurately by X-ray crystal diffraction technique⁴. A single crystal of the compound was mounted along its longer dimension : a axis. By taking rotation and Weissenberg X-ray diffraction photographs, the values of unit cell dimensions were found to be $a=11.62$, $b=26.12$, $c=8.62 \text{ \AA}$ & $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$, volume per unit cell 'V' was calculated to be 2616.294 \AA^3 . No. of molecules per unit cell 'Z'=2. Pycnometric measurement gives the observed density $\rho_{\text{obs}}=3.38 \text{ gml}^{-1}$. From the relation, $\rho_{\text{obs}}=1.66 \text{ M.Z/V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound comes to 2664 against the calculated value 2687.

Measurement of Oxidation State of the Heteroatom : The E.S.R. spectra of the compound were recorded on the powdered sample, using varian 4502-15 E.S.R. spectrometer system, operating at 100 Kcps field modulation. The X ray band spectrum shows only one line at 3500 gauss, $g_{\text{eff}}=1.9919$ (77°K). The diluted sample e.s.r. spectra has several shoulders which permit a reasonably accurate assessment of D value being 0.16 cm^{-1} and λ being 0.1211. There is strong distortion from O_h symmetry. Obviously from the comparative chart, g_{eff} value of the compound indicates chromium to be present in +3 oxidation state having d^3 configuration. The relative spin concentrations were determined by multiplying the peak-to-peak height of the derivative signal by the square of the maximum slope width and absolute concentration were estimated by comparison with standard sample⁵.

Thermal Depolymerisation : The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied in the light of the investigations made by West and Andrieth⁶ and by Babad-Zakhryapin⁷ on a few heteropolytungstic acids. The apparatus used for this purpose was that described by Ray and Sinha⁸ with continuous pumping the depolymerised product, followed by successive weighing using a thermogravimetric balance and estimations at some stages. The dissociation⁴ of the compound was observed at 80° under reduced pressure when twelve molecules of water were lost. Of the rests, seven water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice till 290°, above which they were completely removed. When the temperature was raised still higher, then nearly at 450°, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of molybdenum and chromium which have been confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of 12-heteropoly molybdochromate is $450^\circ \pm 5^\circ$.

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Mahanimbine and Murrayazoline from *Murraya exotica* Linn.* (Syn. *Murraya paniculata*)

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ON chemotaxonomic considerations, we were interested to examine different species of the genus *Murraya* as one of the species *Murraya koenigii* Spreng. is the richest source of carbazole alkaloid¹. *Murraya exotica* has been the subject of numerous investigations² but so far no carbazole alkaloid has been reported from it. We, now report two carbazole alkaloids, mahanimbine, C₂₅H₂₅NO(I), m.p. 94° and murrayazoline C₂₅H₂₅NO(II), m.p. 260° from it.

The neutral fraction of the petroleum ether extract of the stem bark of *Murraya exotica* gave in a very poor yield a crystalline carbazole derivative m.p. 94°. The IR spectrum of the compound (I) showed the presence of -NH and an aromatic system. ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 3359, 1647, 1613, 1575, 1493 cm⁻¹). The UV spectrum of (I) (ν_{\max}^{EtOH} 223, 239, 188, 330, 343 nm with log ϵ 4.55, 4.06, 4.61, 3.90, 3.42) was superimposable with that of mahanimbine³. The compound was identified as mahanimbine by direct comparison (T.L.C. and m.m.p.).

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From the petroleum ether extract of the powdered leaf of *Murraya exotica* a crystalline colorless neutral Hot-II nitrogenous homogenous compound, m.p. 260°, [α]_D was isolated. The IR spectrum of the compound (II) showed the presence of an aromatic system ($\nu_{\max}^{\text{Nujol}}$ 1627, 1590, 1480, 1375, 1368, 852, 873 cm⁻¹). The UV spectrum (ν_{\max}^{EtOH} 245, 307 nm with log ϵ 4.69, 4.16) was suggestive of the presence of 2-methoxy carbazole chromophore. The physical and analytical data were suggestive of the identity of the compound with murrayazoline which was confirmed by the direct comparison with pure specimen of murrayazoline⁴ (mmp., TLC and UV, IR).

Though the yield of the two compounds are very poor, their occurrence in both the species (*M. exotica* and *M. koenigii*) is taxonomically interesting.

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Chemical Constituents of *Pteris longifolia*

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EARLIER communications^{1,2} from this laboratory reported the isolation and characterisation of wallichoside, β -sitosteryl palmitate, β -sitosterol, Pterosin B and Pterosin C from the alcoholic and benzene extract of the rhizomes of an Indian fern, *Pteris wallichiana* (Pteridaceae) respectively. The present report deals with a thorough and systematic chemical investigations of the benzene extract of the whole plant of *Pteris longifolia* (Pteridaceae) as no phytochemical investigations on this fern have so far been reported. This fern and *Pteris biurata*³ are the only two exceptions in this family so far